

SWeaT Test PCB

Technical Documentation

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PCB intended use

This brief document guides the user to perform simple electrochemical and temperature measurements through the SWeaT PCB. The printed-circuit board (PCB) has to be connected to a personal computer (PC) to work properly by means of a simple mini-USB to USB cable to a PC.

The top view of the PCB, shown in Fig.1, comprises AD8606 precision Instrumentation Amplifiers (IA), and shared ADS115 multichannel high-resolution ADCs, MCP1802 voltage regulators in the power section and a MSP430I2041 microcontroller used to configuration and USB communication through the FTDI230RX module.

Fig. 1. Top view of the SWeaT PCB (9 cm x 8.5 cm).

PCB description

The user can connect his sensors by means of the green screw-connectors. The black headers connectors can be used to test and debug the PCB.

The blue variable resistors, located in the lower side of the PCB (“Trim A” and “Trim REF”) allow the user to set the RE A (REference electrode of the Amperometric section) and the REFERENCE electrode voltage of the left sensor connectors, respectively.

The IA RES footprint lets the user insert a desired through hole resistor changing the Instrumentation Amplifier’s RESistor gain. This device is used to read the temperature value measured by means of a couple of Pt1000 RTD, each of these placed in the RTD1 and RTD2 connectors.

The TIA RES footprint lets the user insert a desired through hole resistor changing the Trans-Impedance Amplifier feedback RESistor. This device is used to read the WE A current (Working Electrode of the Amperometric section).

All the measurements are performed converting an analogical voltage in a digital domain by means of two different 4-channels, 16-bit Delta-Sigma ADC (Analog to Digital converter).

Connection to a Windows PC

- After connecting to the personal computer, you need to find the assigned COM port to our board. To do this, type “device manager” on your control panel settings and find the COM. (See Figure 2).

- Now you are ready to start with the measures. Launch the python script (pcb4EC.py, see “Python User Interface” section of this document for details) and insert the number of assigned COM when asked.
- When the python script is executed for the first time, the COM port is requested to the user through the terminal input method: “Please insert the number of PC’s COM”. If it is all correct, no textual error message will be shown.
- Type the desired function (see “Python User Interface” for details) and press the Enter button.
- The PCB elaborates the request and the answer will appear on the working window.

Fig. 2. Device manager window. Here, the assigned COM is the COM7.

For UNIX-based systems the communication port is to be found through the “ls /dev/tty*” command.

Custom configurations

The temperature measures are performed by means of two Pt1000 RTD placed in a Wheatstone bridge configuration.

The bridge differential output voltage is read by an Instrumentation Amplifier (IA) is added. The IA’s output voltage is a function of the temperature and thus, using the Temperature(n) function the temperature can be obtained. The IA shows a programmable Gain described by Eq. (1.1).

$$Gain = 1 + \frac{100 \text{ k}\Omega}{R_G} \quad (1.1)$$

If you type Temperature() it means that any resistor is added in the “IA RES” footprint and the R_G of Eq (1.1) is equal to a fixed value of 100k and the Gain result equal to 2. For example, if you add a 123k Ω resistor in the “IA RES” footprint you must type Temperature(123000) and it means that:

$$R_G = \frac{100 \text{ k}\Omega \times 123 \text{ k}\Omega}{100 \text{ k}\Omega + 123 \text{ k}\Omega} = 55.157 \text{ k}\Omega \quad (1.2)$$

Following Eq. (1.1), the new Gain results 2.813. These operations are automatically performed within the script functions, once the function argument is correctly given.

As the Amperometric section is concerned, it is necessary to point out how the WE_A current is derived. Figure 3 shows the schematic view of the Amperometric-readout section.

Fig. 3. Schematic block of the Amperometric-readout section.

By means of the blue variable resistor “TRIM A”, in the bottom left corner of the PCB, it is possible to set the applied voltage at the RE_A electrode. This value can be read through the dedicated function already discussed. On the other hand, the WE_A current (I_{TIA}) is obtained by manipulating the Trans-ImpedanceAmplifier output voltage (V_{TIA}). Since:

$$V_{TIA} = - R_{fb} \times I_{TIA} + 1.65 V \quad (1.3)$$

where:

$$R_{fb} = \frac{10 M\Omega \times TIA_{RES}}{10 M\Omega + TIA_{RES}} \quad (1.4)$$

The dedicated function WE_A_current(n) automatically returns the value of ITIA. The value R_{fb} can be changed in order to obtain the desired conversion factor. For example, if no extra resistor is plugged in the “TIA_RES” footprint, the conversion factor is 1 V/uA.

Schematic View

Layout View

Bill of Materials

Source	G:\My Drive\AMS_Lab\Hardware\Sweat_PCB\sweat_pcb\sweat_pcb.sch					
Date	04/07/2022 16:29:28					
Tool	Eschema (5.1.10)-1					
Component Count	80					
Ref	Value	Part	Footprint	Description	Vendor	
C1	100nF	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C2	100n	Device:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering	Unpolarized capacitor	
C3	100n	Device:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering	Unpolarized capacitor	
C4	4.7u	Device:CP		Capacitors_Tantalum_SMD:CP_Tantalum_Case-B_EIA-3528-21_Hand	Polarized capacitor	
C5	4.7u	MCU_ADC-rescue:CP		Capacitors_Tantalum_SMD:CP_Tantalum_Case-B_EIA-3528-21_Hand		
C6	4.7u	MCU_ADC-rescue:CP		Capacitors_Tantalum_SMD:CP_Tantalum_Case-B_EIA-3528-21_Hand		
C7	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C8	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C9	100n	Device:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering	Unpolarized capacitor	
C10	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C11	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C12	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C13	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C14	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C15	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C16	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C17	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C18	470n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C19	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C20	1n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C21	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C22	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C23	10n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C24	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
C25	100n	MCU_ADC-rescue:C		Capacitors_SMD:C_0805_HandSoldering		
D1	LED	Device:LED	LEDs:LED_0603_HandSoldering	LEDs:LED_0603_HandSoldering	Light emitting diode	
D2	LED	MCU_ADC-rescue:LED		LEDs:LED_0603_HandSoldering		
D3	LED	MCU_ADC-rescue:LED		LEDs:LED_0603_HandSoldering		
J1	USB_OTG	conn:USB_OTG	Lib_microcreate:USB_Micro-B_AmphenoL10103594-0001LF_Horizontal		USB mini/micro connector	
J2	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x02_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J3	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x02_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J4	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x02_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J5	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x02_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J6	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x02_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J7	Conn_01x07	conn:Conn_01x07	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x07_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x07	
J8	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J9	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J10	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Resistors_THTR_Axial_DIN0516_L1.5x5mm_D5.0mm_P20.32mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J11	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J12	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J13	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J14	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J15	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x02_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J16	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J17	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Lib_2_TerminalBlock_Phoenix_MKDS-1.5-2-5.08_1x02_P5.08mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J18	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Pin_Headers:Pin_Header_Straight_1x02_Pitch2.54mm		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
J19	Conn_01x02	conn:Conn_01x02	Resistors_THTR_Axial_DIN0516_L1.5x5mm_D5.0mm_P20.32mm_Horizontal		Generic connector, single row, 01x02	
L1	Ferrite_Bead	Device:Ferrite_Bead		Resistors_SMD:R_0603_HandSoldering	Ferrite bead	
R1	100k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R2	1.5k	Device:R	Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering	Resistor		
R3	1.5k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R4	1.5k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R5	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R6	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R7	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R8	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R9	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R10	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R11	1k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R12	1k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R13	10k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R14	10k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R15	100k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R16	47k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R17	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R18	1.0k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R19	100k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R20	100k	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
R21	10M	MCU_ADC-rescue:R		Resistors_SMD:R_0805_HandSoldering		
RV1	50k	Device:R_POT_TRIM		Potentiometers:Potentiometer_Trimmer_Bourns_3296W	Trim-potentiometer	
RV2	50k	Device:R_POT_TRIM		Potentiometers:Potentiometer_Trimmer_Bourns_3296W	Trim-potentiometer	
U1	MCP1802	MCU_ADC-rescue:MCP1802	TO_SOT_Packages_SMD:SOT-23-5_HandSoldering			
U2	MCP1802	MCU_ADC-rescue:MCP1802	TO_SOT_Packages_SMD:SOT-23-5_HandSoldering			
U3	FT230XS	Interface_USB1:FT230XS	Housings_SSOP:QSOP-16_3.9x4.9mm_Pitch0.635mm		Full Speed USB to Basic UART, SSOP-16	
U4	MSP430I2041	MCU_ADC-rescue:MSP430I2041	Housings_SSOP:TSSOP-28_4.4x9.7mm_Pitch0.65mm			
U5	AD8604ARUZ	ad8604aruz:AD8604ARUZ	Housings_SSOP:TSSOP-14_4.4x5mm_Pitch0.65mm			
U6	INA333xDGK	Amplifier_Instrumentation2:INA333xDGK	Housings_SSOP:VSSOP-8_3.0x3.0mm_Pitch0.65mm			
U7	ADS1115IDGS	MCU_ADC-rescue:ADS1115IDGS	Housings_SSOP:MSOP-10_3x3mm_Pitch0.5mm			
U8	AD8604ARUZ	ad8604aruz:AD8604ARUZ	Housings_SSOP:TSSOP-14_4.4x5mm_Pitch0.65mm			
U9	ADS1115IDGS	MCU_ADC-rescue:ADS1115IDGS	Housings_SSOP:MSOP-10_3x3mm_Pitch0.5mm			

Python User Interface

Files available at: <https://github.com/michele-dei/SWeaT>. Here we report the quick start script “myscript.py” in the same repository. The script has been tested on a Ubuntu 18.04.5 LTS system with Python 3.6.9.

```
# Minimal use-case examples of pcb4ec
from pcb4ec import session

ex1 = """
#-----
# 1: START SESSION WITH DEFAULT CONFIGURATION
#-----
"""
print(ex1)
# 1.1 Start session after connecting the device to the USB port;
# the user will be asked to select a port from a list of detected ports.
ss1 = session()
# 1.2 Use the read method to read the temperature channel
value = ss1.read('TEMP')
print(value)
# 1.3 Get the channel identifiers
ss1.read()
# 1.4 Make an acquisition with standard defaults
data = ss1()
print(data)
# 1.5 Make a second acquisition and check acquisition journal
ss1()
print(ss1.acquisition)

ex2 = """
#-----
# 2: SESSION WITH CUSTOM CONFIGURATIONS EXAMPLE
#-----
"""
print(ex2)
# 2.1 Silently start session with known device_port
ss2 = session(device_port='/dev/ttyUSB0', verbose=False)
# 2.2 Acquisition with custom channel list and settings + write to file (autogenerated)
d = ss2(['ISE1', 'ISE2', 'TEMP'], verbose=True, nacquisions=5, timestep=2.5, file=True)
print(d)
print('CSV file created in folder')
# 2.3 Change PCB physical settings, e.g. by adding a 20k resistor to IA RES socket
ss2.physical_settings(RIA_socket=20e3)
# 2.4 Acquisition with custom settings + write to file
print('Starting now a silent acquisition')
d2 = ss2('ALL', verbose=False, nacquisions=10, timestep=.5, file='myscript-acquisition-example.txt')
print('Silent acquisition ended. Check "myscript-acquisition-example.txt" in folder')
```